

PROSPECTS FOR THE CLUSTER ACTIVITY IN THE AGRICULTURAL FIELD: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS*Maisuradze I.**Doctor of Economics (Ph. D.)**Gori, Georgia***Abstract**

This article explores the prospects of cluster activity in the agricultural sector, highlighting the problems faced and potential solutions. The article aims to provide insights into overcoming these obstacles and optimizing cluster performance by analyzing the challenges faced by clusters in the agricultural industry. The findings and recommendations presented in this article enhance the effectiveness and sustainability of cluster initiatives in the agriculture sector.

Keywords: Agriculture products, cooperation processes, export potential, fruit and vegetable industry, clusters, cooperation.

Introduction

As a result of economic liberalization and the development of science and technology in our country, fundamental changes are taking place in the agricultural sector, as in all other sectors. The development of this area is considered an important priority of the state and society. The main reason for this is that the agricultural sector is the main sector that solves the country's food problems and supplies food industry enterprises with raw materials.

Today the state is interested in exporting industrial products, especially finished products. Therefore, it would not be an exaggeration to say that the industry has begun an important stage of transition to an innovative economy. Simply put, an innovation cluster is a new production method that unites enterprises associated with plowing the land, planting seeds, caring for cotton, harvesting, and deep processing of raw materials into a single team within one complex to achieve a single goal. Thus, when creating a cluster, raw materials go through all stages of processing and become finished export products.

The experience of many developed countries has shown that the place and importance of clusters in ensuring stable economic development, increasing innovation activity, and producing competitive products is very high.

Literature Review and Research Methodology

One of the ideas put forward by the Prime Minister of Georgia is one of the innovative ideas in developing the agricultural sector and ensuring the competitiveness of manufactured products - this is an important business entity that has a positive impact on the welfare, standard, and quality of life of the population, to widely introduce the cluster system in the country and bring agriculture to high results.

As the Prime Minister noted, "...we need to ensure the production of high-quality Georgian agricultural products and their entry into the world market. In this case, naturally, the profit will increase several times. In addition, it is necessary to obtain hundreds of types of products, and all of them together increase economic efficiency several times. And most importantly, new jobs will be created."

The cluster system gives its results to achieve high efficiency in agriculture and complete processing of manufactured products.

From the moment we gained independence to the present day, the development of the agricultural sector of our country, due to several problems and difficulties, has not produced the desired results; cases of destruction of up to 35.0% of cultivated fruits, vegetables, and dairy products have been recorded. When identifying the main reason, it turned out that problems such as the storage and transportation of agricultural products, especially the inadequacy of the enterprises of the processing system, and in some cases the obsolescence of their material and technical base, had a negative impact.

The cluster system supported in Georgia is the only system to solve these problems.

The cluster method in agriculture includes processes such as pre-treatment of cultivated fields, planting and caring for crops, and production of finished products from cultivated raw materials. This single technological chain unites enterprises of different functions and makes it possible to deepen the integration of science, education, and production, and to introduce new equipment and technologies into practice.

Another important advantage of agroclusters is the introduction of foreign equipment and technologies into agriculture.

Therefore, the development of the agrocluster system serves as the basis for the development of not only the light industry associated with cotton growing, but also food industry enterprises, the construction materials industry, and the pharmaceutical industry.

The main goal of introducing this system in Georgia and its support is not the sale of agricultural products as raw materials to foreign countries, but the processing of these raw materials in the country and the production of high-quality products under the Georgia brand, improving the standard of living of the population, creating new jobs for ensuring employment of the population, improving decent working conditions.

The Government of Georgia has adopted an Action Plan for organizing cluster activities. As a result, positive results have been achieved in providing the industry with advanced equipment and technologies with the help of cluster enterprises. We believe that in the

future the cluster system should be considered as the main important priority of agriculture.

Today, the rapid development of agriculture and the increase in its economic efficiency are associated with the cluster system. Shortly it will become the locomotive of the agricultural sector. Therefore, the more industrialized agriculture is, the more the country's export potential will increase and the country's socio-economic indicators will improve.

A cluster is a collection of enterprises united in a single technological chain, a link that unites different segments of the population, and at the same time an important stage in the transition to an innovative economy in the industry. Because thanks to the cluster, raw materials go through all stages of processing and become finished products for export. In simple terms, the cluster system essentially includes all types of activities within the complex: from plowing the land, planting seeds, caring for cotton, harvesting, and processing.

In these processes, the interests of all producers are harmonized. That is, from the manufacturer to its processors, all employees are equally responsible for the quality of the products. As a result, part of the additional value arising from the sale of the final product increased among all participants in the cluster. This incentive motivates them to work hard for more than just that. The cluster is distinguished not only by its high economic efficiency but also by its social innovation.

Analysis and Results

Cluster production of agricultural products on farms is considered the most important task.

In the traditional agricultural regions of Georgia - Kvemo Kartli, Shida Kartli, and Kakheti, special attention is paid to the introduction of a cluster system in the field of agriculture. These are regions with high productivity and yield, especially in the growing of grapes, fruits, vegetables, and grain crops.

The number of farms in the regions of Kartli and Kakheti is 12,292, of which 1,874 are grain, 195 are horticultural, 447 are horticultural and grape, 382 are grape, 361 are vegetable, 200 are vegetable and grain, 1,551 are livestock. farms and 465 specialized in the production of agricultural products in other areas.

In 2023, 614 agricultural projects were implemented and 5,595 new jobs were created.

Analyzing by area, 261 out of 376 projects (69%) were in the livestock sector, 28 out of 39 (72%) in the poultry sector, 34 out of 39 (87%) in the fisheries sector, and 14 out of 15 in the fisheries sector. beekeeping sector (93%), 59 out of 65 (91) in greenhouse farming, 3 out of 5 (60) in rabbit farming, 7 out of 13 (54) in camel farming, 9 out of 11 (82) in sheep farming, 11 out of 1 in horticulture 4 (36%), refrigeration equipment 4 out of 6 (67%), drip irrigation 7 (100%), other agricultural sectors 10 out of 12 (83%) projects were implemented.

This project, implemented in the region, makes a significant contribution to the economy of the region and creates the basis for improving the living standards of agricultural workers and increasing the income of their families.

The use of the cluster method is of great importance, especially for regions where enterprises are

connected. Clusters play an important role in strengthening the economic independence of regions. This approach allows us to identify economically priority sectors and projects. One of the main advantages of the cluster approach in the development of the regional economy is the strengthening of the role of economic factors and the reduction of the role of administrative factors.

The role of regional administrations is high only at the initial stage. For example, when organizing new clusters taking into account the interests of a given region, the role of the regional administration in the selection of promising clusters is high. In the future, the role of regional administrations will decrease and laws and factors of a market economy will come to the fore. The role of regional authorities will be to support the most important and promising clusters and regulate the "rules of the game."

To support the state's development of a modern viticulture and winemaking cluster, for the needs of which equipment, special vehicles, working machines, animals and plants, veterinary drugs, raw materials, and materials that are not produced in Georgia are imported. Goods for this cluster may be exempt from customs duties.

A few months after the creation of the first agricultural cluster, the Government decided to apply this practice on a large scale to the wine industry. In all regions of the republic, 16 winemaking clusters were created on approximately the same conditions, including tax benefits provided to the first agricultural cluster, government support, independence in activity, and other similar conditions.

In addition, wine clusters are provided with some benefits for the development and support of the industry, including:

- advances are provided to farms by the relevant organizers of wine production in the amounts and on the terms stipulated by the contract;
- to finance the production and supply of cotton raw materials, the organizers of cotton-textile production are allocated loans from the State Support Fund for Agriculture under the Ministry of Finance;
- Loans to organizers of wine production are allocated from savings funds at a rate of no more than 3% per year.

In total, in 2022, more than ten clusters cultivated grapes on 51% of the land allocated for viticulture, and as a result of the creation of new capacities and clusters, 78% of the grapes and wine produced in 2027 will be processed in these regions of Georgia.

By 2027, the share of finished goods production will be increased from 40 percent to at least 60 percent.

Today, internal and external trends in the processes of transformation of agriculture are interconnected - increasing the strategic importance of agricultural development in the context of worsening food problems in the world, and this requires the development of positive experience in using the latest scientific and technical achievements of the world economy.

It is also necessary to take into account an objective assessment of negative trends in agricultural production associated with the degradation of arable land and the lack of modern irrigation systems.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Despite the comprehensive measures being implemented, today there are many shortcomings, problems, and sales imbalances in the production, procurement, transportation, storage, processing, and packaging of food products. In addition, from time to time, infrastructural and market problems arise in the domestic and foreign markets of agricultural products. In particular:

- lack of the required amount of raw materials for processing and untimely provision of it (7-35% provided);
- as a result of the purchase of agricultural products by processing enterprises at low prices, their material interest is small;
- when collecting raw or overripe products, a violation of quality due to non-compliance with the collection technology, collection of crushed products;
- due to the lack of special equipment when transporting products, deterioration in quality, and increase in defects;
- lack of special warehouse buildings and freezers for storing agricultural products;
- resources for organizing the production and processing of agricultural products - lack of provision of short-term and long-term soft loans;
- non-optimal location of processing enterprises based on available raw materials;
- lack of qualified specialists in the management and use of technologies of processing enterprises and lack of training in this area in colleges and other higher educational institutions;
- lack of widespread production of glass containers of various sizes and designs for packaging processed products;
- lack of widespread advertising of agricultural processing.

That is why a comprehensive in-depth analysis of the development trends of these processes in a certain period, the study of specific causes, and the identification of existing opportunities in this regard serve as an important factor in further increasing the efficiency of

this industry and identifying priority directions for its development.

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